

Human Development in South Asia – A Comparative Analysis

Manoj Kumar¹ and Beby Kumari²

¹Assistant Professor (Economics), GNDU College, Narot Jaimal Singh Pathankot. PB.

² Assistant Professor (Economics), Govt. PG College, Chamba. HP.

Abstract

Human development is one of the most important component of social sector development and role of human development in facilitating social and economic progress is well recognised. For many years growth has been a major economic goal of policy makers as delivering a larger quantity of goods and services is the best way to improve people's standard of living. But quality of people's lives can be poor in the midst of plenty so undoubtedly more economic growth is needed but more attention must go to the structure and quality of that growth-to ensure that it is directed to supporting human development, reducing poverty, reducing inequalities, protecting the environment and ensuring sustainability

In the present study an attempt has been made to compare the human development in South Asia. Countries of South Asia constitute the basic unit of study. The study is entirely based on secondary data collected from the various reports of United Nation Development Programmes. The study revealed that while the countries of South Asia experienced significant improvement in human development index and its various indicators such as Life Expectancy, Expected Years of Schooling, Mean Years of Schooling and GNI Per Capita etc. But the overall human development index in South Asia is constant during study period.

Keywords: Human Development, life expectancy, Gender inequality and South Asia

1. Introduction

Human development is one of the most important component of social sector development and role of human development in facilitating social and economic progress is well recognised. For many years growth has been a major economic goal of policy makers as delivering a larger quantity of goods and services is the best way to improve people's standard of living. But quality of people's lives can be poor in the midst of plenty so undoubtedly more economic growth is needed but more attention must go to the structure and quality of that growth-to ensure that it is directed to supporting human development, reducing poverty, reducing inequalities, protecting the environment and ensuring sustainability.

South Asia, in general, and countries in the region (especially India), in particular, have experienced unprecedented growth since 1991s. It helped in poverty reduction and raised the human development index. However, though there is hardly any improvement in the relative HDI ranking. Despite the high growth rate, the absolute number of people in poverty has not gone down, and health and education are still areas of serious concern. The region is still grappling with the problems of human development, both in absolute and relative terms.

Amartya Sen also emphasized that the case of human well being is freedom of choice. Both the fasting monk and the starving pauper may be hungry-the difference is that one exercises a free choice, and the other does not. Human development goes far beyond income and growth

to cover the full flourishing of all human capabilities. Human development reports have defined Human Development as the process of enlarging people's choices. The most critical areas are to lead a long and healthy life, to be educated and to enjoy a decent standard of living.

The region has to increase economic growth. It also needs to focus on the character of the growth process, including its equity and sustainability. The agenda for achieving the new patterns of people-centred growth must include. Accelerating economic growth to improve human development with special focus on education, health and population control. Formulating employment generating growth strategies to ensure inclusion of women, youth, uneducated, unskilled, minorities and disabled and ensuring the long-term sustainability of growth by giving more attention to poverty reduction and people's empowerment.

2. Objective of the Study

The present study aims at analysing and comparing the human development in south asia with special reference to Values of Human Development Index, Life Expectancy, Expected Years of Schooling, Mean Years of Schooling and GNI Per Capita, Gender Inequality, Maternal Mortality Rate and Infant Mortality rate for the period from 2011 to 2014.

3. Database

The present study is entirely based on secondary data collected from United Nations Development Programme and Mehbub ul haq centre. The South Asian countries constitute the basic unit of study.

4. Methods of Study

In present study the following indicator used to analysing and comparing the human development in South Asia.

- Values of Human Development Index,
- Life Expectancy,
- Expected Years of Schooling,
- Mean Years of Schooling,
- GNI Per Capita,
- Gender Inequality,
- Maternal Mortality Rate and
- Infant Mortality rate.

In order to find out the growth of human development, compound growth rate is calculated by using this formula:

$$r = \left(\frac{A_n}{A_0}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1$$

Where r is the rate of growth A_n is the value in nth year and A_0 is the value in the base year and n is the number of years.

Further to find out the extent of inter country disparities, the technique of coefficient of variation is used.

$$\text{Coefficient of Variation} = \frac{SD}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

SD: Standard Deviation

\bar{x} : Mean

5. Study Area:

Southern Asia is a term used to represent the southern region of the Asian continent, which comprises the sub-Himalayan SAARC countries and, for some authorities, adjoining countries to the west and east. The current territories of Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, India, Pakistan and Sri Lanka form the countries of South Asia. South Asia covers about 5.1 million km², which is 11.51% of Asian continent or 3.4% of the world's land surface area. The population of South Asia as about 1.721 billion. India is the largest and fastest growing economy in the region and makes up almost 82% of South Asian economy. India is the only member of powerful G-20 major economies and BRICS from the region. It is the fastest growing major economy in the world and one of the world's fastest registering a growth of 7.3% in financial year 2014-15. Pakistan has the next largest economy and the 5th highest GDP per capita in the region. The current study includes all the countries of South Asia.

6. Result and Discussion

Value of Human Development

According to UNDP (2015), Human Development Report with 73rd rank in world Sri Lanka's rank in South Asia is 1st followed by Maldives 2nd, India 3rd and Bhutan 4th. India with world ranking at 130th rank stood at 3rd position in South Asia. All of South Asian countries recorded human development rank between 73 and 171. Afghanistan with 171 world ranking was at last position in South Asia.

Table 1

Value of Human Development Index (HDI) in South Asia: 2011-2014

Countries	2011	2012	2013	2014	Rank (2014)	Growth rate%
India	0.597	0.600	0.604	0.609	130	0.50
Pakistan	0.527	0.532	0.536	0.538	147	0.52
Bangladesh	0.559	0.563	0.567	0.570	142	0.49
Sri Lanka	0.743	0.749	0.752	0.757	73	0.47
Nepal	0.536	0.540	0.543	0.548	145	0.56
Bhutan	0.582	0.589	0.595	0.605	132	0.97
Afghanistan	0.456	0.463	0.464	0.465	171	0.49
Maldives	0.690	0.695	0.703	0.706	104	
South Asia	0.596	0.596	0.596	0.596	-----	0.00
C.V.	0.45	0.14	1.28	1.61	-----	----
Highest HDI Country	0.941	0.942	0.942	0.944	1	0.08
Lowest HDI Country	0.333	0.342	0.345	0.348	188	1.11

Source: UNDP (2015): *Human Development Report*.

At country level highest growth in value of human development recorded in Bhutan (0.97%) followed by Nepal (0.56%) and Pakistan (0.52%). On the other hand Sri Lanka observed highest value of

human development throughout the study period while its growth rate was at lowest (0.47%). By the value of human development Afghanistan observed lowest place throughout the study period after

Pakistan and Nepal. India with the growth rate (0.50%) in value of human development index secured 3rd rank in South Asia after Sri Lanka and Maldives. The table also revealed that in world the country with rank 1st Norway has the lowest growth rate in value of human development index while the country with 188th rank or lowest place has the highest growth rate (1.11%). Here we can conclude that there was inverse relationship between the rank of human development index and growth rate in the value of human development.

From table 1, it was found that throughout the study period South Asia has the same value for human development (0.596) for all years which reveal that there was no change in overall human develops in South Asia. The growth rate throughout the study period in South Asia was recorded nil (0.00%). The value of Co-efficient of variation revealed that in 2012 the disparities in value of human development were minimum while in 2014 these disparities were maximum. From 2011 to 2012 disparities declined and afterward it rose.

HDI Gap from the highest and lowest HDI Countries

Table 2, revealed that the South Asian countries are far behind the countries with high HDI value, though the gap is getting narrowed down. In 2011,

India was lagging behind the highest HDI country by 0.344. This gap decreased to 0.335 in 2014. Pakistan, too, moved up to narrow-down the gap from 0.414 in 2011 to 0.406 in 2014. Almost similar is the case with Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan and Afghanistan. In South Asia Sri Lanka has the lowest gap in HDI value with the country with high HDI value in world followed by India and Bhutan. On the other hand Afghanistan has the highest gap in HDI value with the country with high HDI value in world followed by Pakistan and Nepal.

Evidently, the improvement in HDI value is relatively better in the case of India than that of Pakistan and Bangladesh, in spite of the fact that India's population size is much bigger than that of Pakistan and Bangladesh. It is evident from table 2 that the South Asian countries have been able to narrow down the gap between them and the high HDI countries over the period of time. And the upward trend is being maintained. At the same time the South Asian countries have been increasing their gap from the countries having lowest HDI value. Nevertheless, some of the low HDI countries have also been trying to catch up with the South Asian countries. The South-Asia as a region has been increasing its gap from the countries having lowest HDI value. But on the other hand gap with the country highest HDI value is also increasing.

Table 2

HDI Gap of South Asian Countries from the highest and lowest HDI Countries: 2011-2014

Countries	2011	2012	2013	2014
India	-0.344 +0.264	-0.342 +0.258	-0.338 +0.259	-0.335 +0.262
Pakistan	-0.414 +0.194	-0.410 +0.190	-0.406 +0.191	-0.406 +0.190
Bangladesh	-0.382 +0.221	-0.379 +0.221	-0.373 +0.222	-0.374 +0.222
Sri Lanka	-0.198 +0.410	-0.193 +0.407	-0.190 +0.407	-0.187 +0.409
Nepal	-0.405 +0.203	-0.402 +0.198	-0.399 +0.198	-0.396 +0.200
Bhutan	-0.359 +0.249	-0.353 +0.247	-0.347 +0.250	-0.339 +0.277
Afghanistan	-0.485 +0.123	-0.479 +0.121	-0.478 +0.119	-0.479 +0.117
Maldives	-0.251 +0.357	-0.247 +0.353	-0.239 +0.358	-0.238 +0.358
South Asia	-0.345 +0.263	-0.346 +0.254	-0.346 +0.252	-0.348 +0.248

Source: Same as in previous table (Computations made by the author).

Notes:

1. The figures with minus sign indicate the difference from the highest HDI country.
2. The figures with + sign indicate the difference between South-Asian Countries and the country with the lowest HDI value.
3. Highest HDI value for 2014 is that of Norway (0.944) and the lowest (0.348) is that of Nigeria.

Life Expectancy, Expected Years of Schooling, Mean Years of Schooling and GNI Per Capita

Table 3 reveal that Maldives was at 1st rank in South Asia for life expectancy followed by Sri Lanka and Bangladesh. India with life expectancy 68 years was at sixth position in South Asia. India's life expectancy (68) was even less than that of South Asia's life expectancy (68.4). Afghanistan and Pakistan with life expectancy of 60.4 and 66.2 respectively were at bottom.

Table 3
Life Expectancy, Expected Years of Schooling, Mean Years of Schooling and GNI Per Capita

Countries	Life Expectancy (2014)	Expected Years of Schooling (2014)	Mean Years of Schooling (2014)	Gap between expected and mean years of schooling	GNI Per Capita (2011 PPP \$)
India	68.0	11.7	5.4	6.3	5,497
Pakistan	66.2	7.8	4.7	4.7	4,866
Bangladesh	71.6	10.0	5.1	4.9	3,191
Sri Lanka	74.9	13.7	10.8	2.9	9,779
Nepal	69.6	12.4	3.3	9.1	2,311
Bhutan	68.2	12.6	3.0	9.6	7,176
Afghanistan	60.4	9.3	3.2	6.1	1,885
Maldives	76.8	13.0	5.8	7.2	12,328
South Asia	68.4	11.2	5.5	5.7	5,605

Source: UNDP (2015): *Human Development Report*.

From the point of view of expected years of schooling Sri Lanka secured 1st position with 13.7 years followed by Bhutan and Nepal 12.6 and 12.4 respectively. Pakistan has the worse condition with expected years of schooling 7.8 years it was at bottom in South Asia.

Table also revealed that the condition of mean years of schooling was worse in all South Asian countries. Except Sri Lanka all countries mean years of schooling vary between 5.8 and 3.3. Majority of the countries have mean years of schooling less than that of the average of South Asia (5.5). Sri Lanka with the mean years of schooling 10.8 secured 1st position in South Asia. Nepal with the mean years of schooling 3.3 secured last position in South Asia. India with the mean years of schooling 5.4 was at 4th position in South Asia.

In terms of gap between expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling the condition was worse in Bhutan (9.6), Nepal (9.1), India (6.3) and Afghanistan (6.1) their gap between expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling was even higher than that of the average of South Asia (5.7). Sri Lanka was at first rank with narrow gap in expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling (2.9) in South Asia followed by Pakistan (4.7) and Bangladesh (4.9). India with gap between expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling (6.3) secured 5th position in South Asia. India's gap between expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling was even higher than that of South Asia (5.7). The position of Pakistan and Bangladesh was better than that of India.

Table 3, also revealed that in terms of GNI per capita. Maldives secured 1st rank with GNI per

capita (12,328) followed by Sri Lanka (9,779) and Bhutan (7,176). India with the GNI per capita (5,497) secured 4th rank in South Asia. India's the GNI per capita was higher than that of South Asia's Average (5,605). Pakistan with 3,191 GNI per capita secured 5th position in South Asia. Half of the south Asian Countries that is India, Sri Lanka, Maldives and Bhutan has the GNI per capita higher than that of South Asia and half of the countries Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal and Afghanistan has lower GNI per capita that South Asia average.

Gender Inequality, Maternal Mortality Rate and Infant Mortality rate

Table 4, revealed that in gender inequality index the position of Maldives was best with gender inequality index 0.243 it secured 1st position in South Asia while Afghanistan with gender inequality index 0.693 was at bottom in South Asia. India with 0.563 gender inequality index was at 7th position. The gender inequality index of average of South Asia (0.536) was better than that of India. Pakistan has the better position in gender inequality index than India. There was also huge gap between the gender inequality index it was varing between 49 to 152. Maldives with world ranking of 49 secured 1st position in South Asia followed by Sri Lanka and Bhutan respectively 2nd and 3rd position in South Asia. Afghanistan with 152 in world ranking was at last position in South Asia after India.

Table 4, also revealed that in case of maternal mortality ratio the situation of Sri Lanka was best and it has the minimum maternal mortality (29) rate. Sri Lanka secured 1st rank in maternal mortality ratio followed by Maldives. There was vast gap between the first two ranking countries (Maldives and Sri Lanka) and rest of the South

Asian countries. The condition was critical in Afghanistan where the maternal mortality rate was highest (400) it was more than double of the South Asia average (183). India with maternal mortality rate of 190 secured 6th position in South Asia. India's maternal mortality rate was higher than that of South Asia. The position of Pakistan was better than India.

Table also highlight that infant mortality rate was minimum in Maldives and Sri Lanka. Sri Lanka with infant mortality rate 8.2 secured 1st position in

South Asia followed by Maldives (8.4). There was also vast gap between the first two ranking countries (Maldives and Sri Lanka) and rest of the South Asian countries. Afghanistan with 70.2 infant mortality rate was at last position in whereas India was at 6th position with infant mortality rate 41.4. Pakistan with 69.0 infant mortality rate was at 7th position in South Asia. Majority of countries have infant mortality rate less than that of South Asia average (43.2) and only two countries Afghanistan and Pakistan has the infant mortality rate higher than that of South Asia.

Table 4

Gender Inequality, Maternal Mortality Rate and Infant Mortality rate in South Asia

Countries	Gender Inequality Index(2014)	Gender Inequality Index Rank (2014)	Maternal Mortality Ratio per/lakh (2013)	Infant Mortality rate per/thousand (2013)
India	0.563	130	190	41.4
Pakistan	0.536	121	170	69.0
Bangladesh	0.503	111	170	33.2
Sri Lanka	0.370	72	29	8.2
Nepal	0.489	108	190	32.2
Bhutan	0.457	97	120	29.7
Afghanistan	0.693	152	400	70.2
Maldives	0.243	49	31	8.4
South Asia	0.536	----	183	43.2

Source: UNDP (2015): *Human Development Report*.

7. Conclusion

On the basis of analysis of data the following conclusion can be drawn:

In South Asia Sri Lanka secured first position in almost every indicator taken to study. While Afghanistan was at the bottom in maximum indicators. Position of India was better in infant mortality rate and life expectancy while for others indicators its condition was worse than that of the average of South Asia. The South-Asia as a region has been lagging behind in terms of human development. In terms of HDI ranking their

position in the world did not improve during the study period. Nevertheless, they have registered a definite improvement in their respective value of HDI and narrowed down their gap with the high HDI countries. Despite the fact, that the region has attained a remarkable improvement in certain indicators related to life expectancy and gender inequality index yet the extent of inequality among the various indicators is quite disturbing. The education gaps by expected years of schooling and mean years of schooling are also very glaring in these countries.

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